

Title: The Role of Robotics in Advancing Assistive Technologies

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INTRODUCTION:

This talk will present the problem of walking for humanoid robots and how this technology can be used for improving human locomotion for below knee amputees. Humanoid robots face many challenges to walk like humans in uncontrolled and natural environments. These challenges can be addressed at the mechanical design and the control design stages. Both the task based design of humanoid robots using dynamic simulation and also the linear and nonlinear control design methods will be discussed. The technology developed for humanoid robots can help humans with amputations to recover their lost locomotion or motor control abilities. The applications include a powered two degree of freedom ankle-foot prosthesis which was tested on a custom designed gait emulator and subsequently on human subjects and amputees.

AIM:

To use the technologies developed in the field of humanoid robotics for assistive walking devices for amputees. Introducing the current state of the art, achievements and challenges to develop a fully functional prosthetic limb.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The development of prostheses requires testing on both humans and gait emulators to increase the repeatability during evaluation experiments. Initially, the ankle foot prosthesis was tested on a gait emulator to test its control system and overall functionality. Subsequently, a study was conducted by the researchers at Michigan Technological University in collaboration with Mayo clinics on two amputees over a three months period in which all the biomechanical parameters of the amputees were recorded to investigate the effectiveness of the powered ankle foot prosthesis in activities of daily living.

RESULTS:

The results show that the developed ankle foot prosthesis is capable of helping the amputees to gain normal walking and its lightweight construction opens up the potential for improving the metabolic cost for amputees.

CONCLUSIONS:

This study showed the effectiveness of using robotic ankle foot prostheses for below knee amputees. The joint motion control system that is often used in humanoid robots was used to provide an effective controller for the powered prosthesis. This device was initially tested on a custom built gait emulator to ensure repeatability and was subsequently tested on amputees.

KEYWORDS:

Ankle foot prostheses; Robotics; Control Systems

BIOGRAPHY:

Houman Dallali received the B.S. degree from the Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran, in 2006; the M.S. degree from The University of Sheffield, U.K., in 2007; and the Ph.D. degree from The University of Manchester, U.K., in 2012, all in electrical and control systems engineering. He was a Post-Doctoral Research Associate at the Department of Advanced Robotics, Italian Institute of Technology, in Genova, Italy, (2012–2015), where he worked on modeling, simulation, and control of CoMan and WALK-MAN humanoid robots. He joined the Human- Interactive Robotics Lab at Michigan Technological University as a Post-Doctoral Research Associate in 2015. His current research is focused on the development of walking control systems for an untethered and powered ankle-foot prosthesis.